

SURFACE MODIFICATION OF CARBON WHISKER BY THE GRAFTING OF POLYMERS

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ABSTRACT

The graft polymerization of various monomers from carbon whisker surface initiated by initiating groups introduced onto the surface was investigated. The radical graft polymerization of vinyl monomers was initiated by azo and peroxyester groups introduced onto the surface to give the corresponding polymer-grafted carbon whisker. The anionic ring-opening alternating copolymerization of epoxides with cyclic acid anhydrides was initiated by potassium carboxylate groups and the corresponding polyesters were grafted onto the surface. In addition, the cationic polymerization of vinyl monomers and ring-opening polymerization of cyclic ethers and lactones were initiated by acylium perchlorate groups introduced onto the surface and the corresponding polymers were grafted onto the surface.

INTRODUCTION

Recently, carbon whisker, i.e., vapor grown carbon fiber, has become applicable to high performance composite materials. To disperse the carbon whisker into a polymer matrix uniformly and to transmit stress from the matrix to the carbon whisker, it is desirable to modify the surface by the grafting of polymers.

On the other hand, we have reported that the radical, anionic, and cationic graft polymerizations are initiated by azo and peroxyester groups, potassium carboxylate groups, and acylium perchlorate groups introduced onto carbon black surface, respectively, to give the corresponding polymer-grafted carbon blacks [1]. In the graft polymerizations, polymer-grafted carbon blacks with a high percentage of grafting were obtained, because of the propagation of grafted polymer from the surface initiating groups.

In the present paper, to modify the surface of carbon whisker, we investigated the grafting of various polymers onto the surface by the radical, anionic and cationic graft polymerization of various monomers initiated by azo and peroxyester, potassium carboxylate (COOK), and acylium perchlorate groups previously introduced onto the surface. In addition, the grafting of polymers by the direct condensation of surface carboxyl groups with terminal hydroxyl and amino groups of polymers in the presence of condensing agent was examined. The properties of polymer-grafted carbon whisker was also discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Carbon Whisker and Reagents Carbon whisker used was obtained from Asahi Chemical Ind. Ltd., Japan. The carbon whisker was extracted with chloroform using a Soxhlet apparatus to remove resinous substances on the surface and dried *in vacuo* at 110°C before use. The fiber diameter and fiber length were determined to be 0.1–0.3 μm and 10–30 μm , respectively, by SEM. The content of phenolic hydroxyl and carboxyl groups was determined to be 0.02 and 0.08 mmol/g, respectively. 4,4'-Azobis(4-cyanopentanoic acid) (ACPA) and 2,2'-azobis[(2-hydroxymethyl)propionitrile] (AHP) were obtained from Wako Pure Chemical Ind., Japan and purified by recrystallization. Guaranteed reagent grade silver perchlorate obtained from Kojima Chemical Ind., Japan was dried at 110°C before use. Monomer and solvents were used after ordinary purification.

Introduction of Carboxyl and Phenolic Hydroxyl Groups To introduce carboxyl and phenolic hydroxyl groups onto the surface, carbon whisker was treated with nitric acid and *n*-butyllithium, respectively. The content of carboxyl and phenolic hydroxyl groups of the treated carbon whisker increased to 0.12 and 0.25 mmol/g, respectively.

Introduction of Azo Groups The introduction of azo groups onto carbon whisker surface was achieved by (1) the reaction of ACPA with isocyanate groups, which were introduced by the treatment with tolylene-2,4-diisocyanate and (2) the reaction of AHP with acyl chloride groups, which were introduced by the treatment of phenolic hydroxyl groups with phthaloyl dichloride. The carbon whiskers obtained from the methods (1) and (2) were abbreviated as CW-Azo 1 and 2, respectively.

Introduction of Peroxyester Groups The introduction of peroxyester groups onto carbon whisker surface was achieved by the reaction of *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide with acyl chloride groups, which were introduced by (1) the reaction of carboxyl groups with thionyl chloride, (2) the reaction of phenolic hydroxyl groups with adipoyl dichloride and (3) with phthaloyl dichloride. The carbon whiskers obtained from the methods (1), (2), and (3) were abbreviated as CW-POE 1, 2, and 3, respectively.

Introduction of COOK Groups The introduction of COOK groups onto the carbon whisker surface was achieved by the neutralization of carboxyl groups with aqueous solution of potassium hydroxide. The carbon whisker was abbreviated as CW-COOK.

Introduction of Acylium Perchlorate Groups The introduction of acylium perchlorate groups onto carbon whisker was achieved by the *pretreatment* of carbon whisker having acyl chloride groups with an excess of silver perchlorate in nitrobenzene. The cationic graft polymerization was initiated by the addition of monomer after the pretreatment. The detailed procedures were described in the previous paper [2]. The carbon whisker having acylium perchlorate groups was abbreviated as CW-APC.

Polymerization Procedures The radical polymerization initiated by CW-Azo and CW-POE was carried out in a vacuum sealed tube with shaking. The anionic polymerization initiated by CW-COOK and the cationic graft polymerization initiated by CW-APC were carried out in a flask under dry nitrogen with stirring using a magnetic stirrer. After the graft polymerization, the contents of the sealed tube and the flask were poured into a large excess of methanol and polymer-grafted carbon whisker containing ungrafted polymer was precipitated. The conversion was determined by the following equation.

$$\text{Conversion (\%)} = (A-B)/B \times 100$$

where A is weight of precipitate obtained and B is weight of carbon whisker charged.

Grafting Reaction with Polymers The grafting reaction of surface carboxyl groups with polymers having terminal amino or hydroxyl groups in the presence of *N,N'*-dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC) was carried out in a flask under nitrogen with stirring.

Percentage of Grafting and Grafting Efficiency To remove ungrafted polymer from the products, the resulting carbon whisker was extracted using a Soxhlet apparatus with a good solvent for ungrafted polymer. The percentage of grafting and grafting efficiency were determined by the following equations.

$$\text{Grafting (\%)} = (A/B) \times 100$$

$$\text{Grafting efficiency (\%)} = (A/C) \times 100$$

where A is weight of grafted polymer, which determined from the weight increment of carbon whisker after the polymerization, B is weight of carbon whisker charged, and C is weight of total polymer formed.

Stability of Polymer-Grafted Carbon Whisker Dispersion The stability of polymer-grafted carbon whisker dispersion in a good solvent for grafted polymer was estimated from carbon whisker content in the dispersion after standing at room temperature. The detailed procedures were described in the previous paper [3].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

INTRODUCTION OF INITIATING GROUPS ONTO CARBON WHISKER

The introduction reactions of azo, peroxyester, COOK, and acylium perchlorate groups onto carbon whisker surface were described in the EXPERIMENTAL section. The introduction of azo groups and peroxyester groups was achieved by the two methods and three methods, respectively.

The content of initiating groups introduced onto CW-Azo 1, CW-Azo 2, CW-POE 1, CW-POE 2, CW-POE 3, CW-COOK, and CW-APC was shown in Table 1. Azo group content was determined by elemental analysis. The content of peroxyester, COOK, and acylium perchlorate groups was determined by titration. As shown in Table 1, the initiating groups were found to be successfully introduced onto carbon whisker surface by the above reactions.

Table 1 Initiating group content of carbon whisker

CW	Functional groups (mmol/g)
CW-Azo 1	0.04
CW-Azo 2	0.07
CW-POE 1	0.06
CW-POE 2	0.05
CW-POE 3	0.17
CW-COOK	0.08
CW-APC	0.05

RADICAL GRAFT POLYMERIZATION

Initiation from Surface Azo Groups Table 2 shows

the results of the polymerization of styrene in the presence of untreated carbon whisker, CW-Azo 1, and CW-Azo 2. The thermal polymerization of styrene was initiated even in the absence of carbon whisker, but the polymerization rate was small. In the presence of untreated carbon whisker, the thermal polymerization was almost completely inhibited.

Table 2 The polymerization of styrene initiated by azo groups introduced onto carbon whisker

CW	Conversion (%)	Grafting (%)
None	1.0	-
Untreated	1.0	0
CW-Azo 1	1.8	13.5
CW-Azo 2	2.0	29.3

CW, 0.10 g; styrene, 10.0 mL ; 70°C; 8 h.

On the contrary, in the presence of CW-Azo 1 and CW-Azo 2, the polymerization of styrene was initiated and polystyrene was grafted onto the carbon whisker surface. The rate of the polymerization and percentage of grafting in the presence of CW-Azo 2 was larger than that of CW-Azo 1, because of higher content of azo groups of CW-Azo 2.

Figure 1 shows the relationship between polymerization time and conversion (or percentage of grafting) in the polymerization of methyl methacrylate (MMA) initiated by CW-Azo 2. The conversion linearly increased with progress of the polymerization. On the other hand, PMMA grafting increased at the initial stage of the polymerization, but no longer increased after about 10 h.

Figure 2 shows the relationship between conversion and grafting efficiency in the graft polymerization shown in Figure 1. It is interesting to note that the grafting efficiency is high, i.e., about 50%, at the initial stage of the polymerization, but immediately decreased with progress of the polymerization. These results are explained as follows: the polymerization of MMA is initiated by both radicals on carbon whisker surface and initiator fragments formed by the thermal decomposition of the surface azo groups as shown in Eq. 1. The radicals formed on the carbon whisker surface initiate the graft polymerization and grafted chains are propagated from the surface. On the other hand, the fragments radicals also initiate the polymerization to produce ungrafted PMMA.

Therefore, at the initial stage of the polymerization, the grafting efficiency become to be about 50%. However, the propagation of grafted polymer from the surface radicals is considered to be gradually inhibited by neighboring grafted polymers and the formation of ungrafted polymer becomes to preferential reaction at the middle and last stage of the polymerization,

Fig.1 Polymerization of MMA initiated by CW-Azo 2. CW, 0.10 g; MMA, 10.0 mL; 70°C.

Fig. 2 Relationship between grafting efficiency and conversion

which decrease the grafting efficiency.

Initiation from Peroxyester Groups Table 3 shows the results of the graft polymerization of *N*-vinylcarbazole (NVC) in the presence of CW-POE 1, 2, and 3. It was found that the polymerization of NVC is initiated by CW-POE 2 and 3 to give PNVC-grafted carbon whisker. However, CW-POE 1 failed to initiate the graft polymerization of NVC. The polymerizations of various vinyl monomers, such as styrene and MMA, were also initiated by CW-POE 2 and 3 to give the corresponding polymer-grafted carbon whiskers, but CW-POE 1 has no ability to initiate the graft polymerization of vinyl monomers.

These results indicates that in the presence of CW-POE 2 and 3, the graft polymerization is initiated by surface radicals on carbon whisker formed by the thermal decomposition of peroxyester groups and grafted polymer chains are propagated from the surface.

On the contrary, peroxyester groups of CW-POE 1 is considered to decompose to give surface phenyl radicals and *tert*-butyloxy radicals as shown in Eq. 2. The surface phenyl radicals seem to be stabilized by polycondensed aromatic rings of carbon whisker surface and has no ability to initiate the polymerization. The initiation of polymerization by *tert*-butyloxy radicals was completely inhibited by the surface phenyl radicals, which is known to act as a strong radical scavenger. The same tendency has been reported by us in the polymerization of vinyl monomers initiated by peroxyester groups introduced onto carbon black surface.

Table 3 Polymerization of NVC initiated by CW-POE

CW	Conversion (%)	Grafting (%)
None	0	-
Untreated	0	0
CW-POE 1	0	-
CW-POE 2	1.6	7.9
CW-POE 3	8.3	11.4

ANIONIC GRAFT POLYMERIZATION

It has been reported that the anionic ring-opening alternating copolymerization of

CW, 0.10 g; NVC (0.5 mol/L in toluene), 10 mL; 70 °C; 8 h.

epoxides with cyclic acid anhydrides are initiated by potassium acetate to give the corresponding polyester. Therefore, the grafting of polyesters onto carbon whisker surface by the copolymerization initiated by COOK groups introduced onto the surface was examined. The introduction of COOK groups onto carbon whisker surface was achieved by the neutralization of carboxyl groups on the surface.

Table 4 shows the results of the copolymerization of styrene oxide (SO) with phthalic anhydride (PAn) under several conditions. Table 4 clearly shows that the anionic copolymerization of SO with PAn is successfully initiated by CW-COOK to give the corresponding polyester-grafted carbon whisker.

Figure 3 shows the relationship between conversion and percentage of grafting in the copolymerization of SO with PAn and SO with succinic anhydride (SAn). The percentage of grafting of polyesters increased with increasing conversion.

The grafting of various polyesters onto carbon whisker by the anionic ring-opening copolymerization of several epoxides with cyclic acid anhydrides initiated by CW-COOK was examined. The results are summarized in Table 5. Epoxides used were SO, epichlorohydrin (ECH), glycidyl phenyl ether (GPE), and glycidyl methacrylate (GMA). Cyclic acid anhydrides used were PAn, maleic anhydride (MAn), and SAn. It is apparent that the anionic ring-opening copolymerization of epoxides with cyclic acid anhydrides is initiated by CW-COOK and the corresponding polyesters are grafted onto carbon whisker based on the propagation of polyester from COOK groups.

It is apparent that the anionic ring-opening copolymerization of epoxides with cyclic acid anhydrides is initiated by CW-COOK and the corresponding polyesters are grafted onto carbon whisker based on the propagation of polyester from COOK groups.

Table 4 Anionic copolymerization of SO with PAn under several conditions

CW	SO (mol)	PAn (mol)	Conversion (%)	Grafting (%)
None	0.02	0.02	0	-
Untreated	0.02	0.02	0	0
CW-COOK	0.02	-	0	0
CW-COOK	-	0.02	0	0
CW-COOK	0.02	0.02	24.8	44.0

CW, 0.10 g; 120°C; 1 h.

Fig.3 Relationship between conversion and percentage of grafting

Table 5 Grafting of polyesters onto carbon whisker by the copolymerization of epoxides with cyclic acid anhydrides

Epoxide	Anhydride	Time (h)	Conversion (%)	Grafting (%)
SO	PAn	12	79.3	91.0
SO	MAn	12	65.8	75.0
SO	SAn	12	50.5	87.3
ECH	PAn	12	5.6	71.1
ECH	SAn	12	48.1	55.9
GPE	PAn	48	58.3	73.4
GMA	PAn	12	80.1	Gelation

CW, 0.10 g; epoxide=anhydride=0.02 mol; 120°C.

CATIONIC GRAFT POLYMERIZATION

The introduction of acylium perchlorate groups onto carbon whisker surface, *pretreatment*, was achieved by the reaction of acyl chloride groups with silver perchlorate. It was found that the cationic polymerization of vinyl monomers was initiated by acylium perchlorate groups

Fig.4 Relationship between conversion and percentage of polystyrene grafting in the polymerization initiated by CW-APC

Fig.5 Effect of temperature on the grafting of polystyrene

formed *in situ* by the *pretreatment* and the corresponding polymers were grafted onto the surface based on the propagation of grafted polymer from the surface.

Figure 4 shows the relationship between conversion and percentage of grafting (or grafting efficiency) in the polymerization of styrene initiated by CW-APC. It is apparent that the percentage of polystyrene grafting immediately increased to 42.5% with increasing conversion. On the contrary, the grafting efficiency was very high during the first stage of the polymerization, but immediately decreased with increasing conversion.

These results indicates that the grafted polymer is propagated from the surface acylium perchlorate groups on carbon whisker and the ungrafted polymer is gradually formed by a chain transfer reaction of growing polymer cation to the monomer. And then, at the last stage of the polymerization, ungrafted polymer is preferentially formed.

Figure 5 shows the effect of temperature on the grafting of polystyrene onto carbon whisker surface. The percentage of grafting decreased with increasing polymerization temperature. The result indicates that the formation of ungrafted polystyrene enhanced by increasing polymerization temperature, because the increasing temperature causes in the rate of chain transfer reaction of growing polymer cation.

In addition, CW-APC has an ability to initiate the cationic ring-opening polymerization of cyclic ethers, lactones, and cyclic acetals to give polyether-grafted, polyester-grafted, and polyacetal-grafted carbon whisker.

REACTION OF CARBON WHISKER WITH FUNCTIONAL POLYMERS

The grafting reaction by the direct condensation of carboxyl groups on carbon whisker with polymers having terminal hydroxyl or amino groups in the presence of DCC as a condensing agent was investigated (Eq. 3). Functional polymers used were hydroxyl-terminated polydimethylsiloxane (SDO) and amino-terminated polydimethylsiloxane (SDA).

Table 6 shows the results of the grafting reaction of SDA and SDO under several conditions. In the absence of DCC, the grafting of polymers onto the surface was very small: this is due to adsorption of polymers onto the surface. On the contrary, SDO and SDA were grafted onto

Table 6 Grafting reaction of polymers onto carbon whisker by direct condensation in the presence of DCC

Condensing agent	Polymer	Mn x 10 ⁻³	Grafting (%)
None	SDA	3.9	trace
DCC	SDA	3.9	8.7
None	SDO	3.2	trace
DCC	SDO	3.2	10.4

CW, 0.10 g; polymer, 2.5 mmol; DCC, 0.025 g; THF, 5.0 mL; 60°C; 3 h.

Fig. 6 Stability of dispersion of PMMA-grafted CW in THF

the surface of carbon whisker. This indicates that carboxyl groups on carbon whisker reacted with terminal hydroxyl or amino groups of SDO and SDA and these polymers were grafted onto the surface with ester and amid bonds, respectively. The number of grafted polymer chains on the surface decreased with increasing molecular weight of the functional polymers.

Furthermore, the grafting reaction of SDO and SDA by the direct condensation using condensing agents such as SOCl_2/N -methyl-2-pyrrolidone and SOCl_2 /pyridine was examined.

PROPERTIES OF POLYMER-GRAFTED CARBON WHISKER

The stability of PMMA-grafted carbon whisker dispersion in THF was compared with that of untreated carbon whisker. The results are shown in Figure 6. Ungrafted carbon whisker immediately precipitated. On the contrary, PMMA-grafted carbon whisker gave a stable colloidal dispersion in THF. This indicates that grafted polymer chains interfere with the aggregation of carbon whisker.

The surface of PMMA-grafted carbon whisker was hydrophobic, but the surface of NVPD-grafted carbon whisker was hydrophilic. This indicates that by the grafting of polymers onto the surface, the wettability of carbon whisker surface is able to control.

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